

Coupled Reactor–Shielding Optimization for a Space Heat Pipe Reactor (HPR)

Francisco Szmandiuk¹, Pablo Rubiolo¹, Martín Marone¹, Nicolas Capellan¹, Fabien Castanet²

¹LPSC, Univ. Grenoble Alpes, Grenoble INP, Grenoble, France;
²CNES, Toulouse, France;

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ABSTRACT

Nuclear Electric Propulsion (NEP) systems offer high specific impulse and continuous thrust, making NEP a strong candidate for future cargo and deep-space missions. This work investigates the coupled design of the reactor core and reactor shielding in a fast-neutron-spectrum Heat-Pipe Reactor (HPR) using monolithic UMo fuel. The analysis is performed with PRESTO, a multiphysics optimization tool for NEP system design, which has been enhanced to include neutron and gamma transport models as well as simplified thermal models for HPR shielding. These enhancements enable the simultaneous optimization of the reactor and shielding while accounting for key nuclear, thermal, and radiological constraints in both subsystems. The results from the coupled reactor–shielding optimization show that increasing the number of heat pipes significantly affects the thermal performance of the shielding. HPR configurations with more heat pipes traversing the shielding require thicker insulation to prevent overheating of the LiH shielding material, leading to substantial increases in total system mass. Moreover, the design studies show that the outer surface of the shielding must be thermally insulated to avoid radiative losses, which without external thermal insulation can reach up to 30% of the reactor power in some configurations. A maximum allowable heat loss from the shielding to space must therefore be imposed during design optimization. When both maximum-temperature and heat-loss constraints are applied, a clear trade-off emerges: excessively reducing heat losses increases system mass unless the number of heat pipes is limited. Consequently, reactors with fewer heat pipes exhibit lower total masses. The coupled optimizations also show that the optimal Height-to-Diameter (H/D) ratio of the reactor core is affected by the coupled design process. Overall, performing a coupled optimization of these two NEP subsystems yields mass savings of approximately 10% relative to the uncoupled design process.

Keywords: NEP, Heat Pipe Reactor, Design Optimization, Reactor Shielding

1. INTRODUCTION

Nuclear Electric Propulsion (NEP) systems are among the most promising technologies for future cargo missions and deep-space exploration, offering high specific impulse and continuous thrust over long durations. In these systems, a nuclear reactor generates thermal energy that is converted into electricity to power ion thrusters, which accelerate a propellant to produce thrust. The overall NEP architecture integrates several tightly coupled subsystems: the nuclear reactor, the neutron and gamma shielding, the power-conversion unit, the radiators that reject residual heat to space, and the electric thrusters with their associated propellant tanks.

One particular class of NEP reactors is the Heat Pipe Reactor, which relies on heat pipes to transport the heat produced by fission to the power-conversion system. Heat pipes (HPs) are passive heat-transfer devices that efficiently transport thermal energy by exploiting the latent heat of vaporization and condensation of a working fluid such as water or sodium. In an HPR, heat is absorbed in the evaporator section of the heat pipe, located within the nuclear fuel, where the working fluid evaporates. The resulting vapor then flows to the condenser section, located in the power-conversion system (typically a Stirling engine), where it releases heat and condenses. The return of the liquid to the evaporator is driven by capillary forces generated within a porous wick.

In space applications, the waste heat that cannot be converted into electricity must be rejected to space. Since radiators dissipate heat through thermal radiation, their required surface area and mass scale

approximately with the inverse fourth power of the operating temperature. Therefore, heat pipes in HPRs are designed to operate at high temperatures to improve conversion efficiency and enable more compact radiator designs (i.e., limiting the radiator mass). However, these high operating temperatures impose important thermal constraints on other components of the reactor and NEP subsystems, such as the reactor shielding. The primary function of the shielding is to attenuate neutron and gamma fluxes from the reactor, thereby protecting other NEP subsystems such as the power-conversion and radiator systems, as well as the payload. Because routing or bending heat pipes around the reactor shielding is mechanically complex and significantly reduces heat-transport efficiency of HPs, most HPR configurations in the tens-of-kilowatts power range allow the HPs to pass directly through the shielding structure.

In typical HPR for NEP, heat is extracted from the core through sodium heat pipes operating above 1000 K, which must thus pass through the shielding to reach the power conversion unit. On the other hand, in most NEP designs, the shielding structure contains lithium hydride (LiH), a standard material for space reactors due to its low density and excellent neutron-attenuation properties. However, LiH has a relatively low melting point (≈ 692 °C or 965 K), which is close to the operating temperatures of both the reactor and the heat pipes. For this reason, direct contact between the heat pipes and the shielding must be avoided to prevent material degradation. Moreover, controlling the heat transfer from the heat pipes to the shielding is also necessary to avoid an excessive loss of heat that would otherwise reduce the thermal energy available for power conversion and thus decrease the overall efficiency of the NEP system.

To prevent overheating of the LiH and to reduce heat losses from the heat pipes to the reactor shielding, a thermal insulation layer has to be introduced between the heat pipes and the shielding, as well as on the outer surface of the shielding. This insulation is sufficiently large to modify neutron and gamma transport within the shielding, thereby affecting its effectiveness. Consequently, a coupling between the core and the shielding design arises not only through the neutron and gamma source emitted by the reactor core, but also through the operating temperature of the heat pipes.

One key parameter in any NEP concept is the total system mass, which determines the NEP specific electric power (i.e., the electric power per unit mass) and must be minimized in order to improve overall system performance. Two of the largest contributors to the total mass are the reactor core and the reactor shielding. Therefore, the optimization of these two components must account for their design couplings.

In this work, the impact of the coupling between the reactor core and the shielding of a heat-pipe reactor using monolithic UMo fuel is analysed using a multiphysics design tool called PRESTO (NEP Rocket Design Tool) [1]. The main objective of PRESTO is to support preliminary design and optimization of NEP systems, enabling the identification of configurations that optimize selected figures of merit, such as total system mass or specific electric power. In NEP systems, achieving high specific electric power is essential for mission competitiveness, as previously examined in Ref. [2]. PRESTO has been updated by integrating neutron and gamma transport models to perform particle-transport calculations in the NEP reactor shielding. In addition, simplified thermal models have been incorporated into the shielding module to account for heat losses from the heat pipes into the shielding and from the shielding to space. The tool can therefore optimize the reactor and shielding designs simultaneously, while considering key nuclear, thermal, and radiological design constraints in both subsystems. This paper presents the design results obtained for these two critical NEP subsystems using the tool, and discusses the key findings of the study.

2. SYSTEM MODEL AND OPTIMIZATION FRAMEWORK

2.1. Reactor and Shielding Model

2.1.1. Reactor Model

The reactor analysed in this work is a fast-spectrum Heat Pipe Reactor (HPR) concept employing a metallic U-7.65Mo HALEU fuel (20% enrichment), sodium heat pipes, and a beryllium reflector. Its overall configuration is inspired by the design adopted in the KRUSTY project Ref. [3], but it has been adapted to operate with lower fuel enrichment. The fuel is arranged as a metallic matrix into which the

heat pipes are inserted in a hexagonal lattice (Fig. 1). Each heat pipe consists of a Haynes-230 structural wall, a nickel wick, and sodium as the working fluid. The fuel region is surrounded by a beryllium reflector.

The geometric parameters defining the reactor model include the apothem of the fuel unit cell ($apot$), the heat-pipe radius (r_{hp}), the reflector thickness (t_r) and the height to diameter ratio (H/D).

The multifysics tool PRESTO incorporates several operational and material-performance limits for this particular reactor model, namely: The melting temperature of all reactor materials, irradiation-induced damage limits for beryllium and U-7.65Mo fuel and the thermal-transport limits of the heat pipes

More details on the neutronic and thermal-hydraulic models for the fast-spectrum Heat Pipe Reactor (HPR) with a monolithic fuel are given in [4].

Figure 1. Heat Pipe Reactor SERPENT model.

2.1.2. Shielding Neutronic Model

The shielding model is based on SERPENT Monte Carlo code transport simulations that account for both neutron and gamma propagation from the reactor core to the conversion systems + payload region. All neutrons and gammas crossing S_i , including those originating from the lateral (radial) surfaces of the reactor and streaming toward the shadow shield, are recorded (see Fig. 2). For each escaping neutron or photon, the position, direction cosines, and energy are recorded together with the net outgoing neutron current. This information is then used to define the input source for the shielding model, normalized to a reactor thermal power of 1 W. Scaling to any reactor power level is then performed linearly with the thermal power.

The shielding is modelled as a truncated conical assembly composed of neutron-shielding layers made of lithium hydride (LiH), selected for its excellent neutron attenuation and low density, and a gamma-shielding layer made of tungsten (W), providing attenuation of reactor prompt and capture gammas produced.

The geometry is characterized by the dimensions of the reactor R_c and H_c (since the shielding should follow the shadow of the reactor), the opening angle α , the gap between the reactor and shielding and the total shielding length $L_{sh} = L_{n1} + L_\gamma + L_{n2}$, which is divided into neutron and gamma sections of lengths L_{n1} , L_{n2} and L_γ respectively as shown in Fig. 2. The gamma-shielding section is located at roughly 30% of the distance from the beginning of the shielding. This position provides a very good compromise between reducing gamma production from neutron capture in tungsten and limiting the mass penalty that would arise from increasing the radius of the gamma-shielding section dictated by the opening angle.

The presence of the HPs in the shielding is modelled by adjusting the theoretical density ρ_0 of the LiH by an effective density reduction factor F_{dens} which is proportional to the porosity of the shielding section traversed by the heat pipes and the associated thermal insulation. The factor F_{dens} depends thus on the number and diameter of the HPs and on the thickness of the thermal insulation between the HPs and the LiH. The effective density of this section of the shielding is thus calculated as follows: $\rho^* = F_{dens} \cdot \rho_0$. As F_{dens} decreases, the neutron and gamma attenuation lengths must be increased to maintain the prescribed radiation limits on the conversion systems and payload side.

At the outer boundary (surface S_2), the average neutron fluence and photon dose rate are tallied over the full cross section. Surface S_2 is defined at the shield exit plane and therefore moves with the total shielding thickness L_{sh} . In this work the neutron fluence limit and gamma dose adopted are 1×10^{12} n/cm² and 1 Mrad respectively according to the limits established for Silicon in Ref. [5]. These values can however be modified depending on the adopted design limits.

Figure 2. Neutron and gamma Shielding SERPENT model.

2.1.3. Shielding Thermal Model

For thermal analyses, the shielding is simplified as a right circular cylinder of axial length L and radius R_{sh} , traversed by n_{HP} heat pipes (HPs) arranged in concentric rings. Each HP of radius r_{HP} is surrounded by an annulus of thermal insulation with thickness t_{ins} . The radial temperature distribution in the shielding is obtained by solving the steady-state, one-dimensional heat equation with internal heat generation:

$$T(r) = -\frac{q_v}{4k_{eq}}r^2 + T_{max} \quad (1)$$

where q_v is the volumetric heat source representing the net heat transferred to the shielding by the HP array. Equation (1) is obtained by modeling the shielding as a porous medium with an equivalent uniform thermal conductivity of k_{eq} calculated based on the porosity as follows:

$$k_{eq} = (1 - p) \cdot k_{sh} \quad (2)$$

where k_{sh} is the thermal conductivity of the shielding material and p is the porosity fraction associated with the HPs and their thermal insulation:

$$p = (n_{HP} A_{IHP})/A_{sh}, \quad A_{IHP} = \pi r_{IHP}^2, \quad r_{IHP} = r_{HP} + t_{insul} \quad (3)$$

where A_{IHP} is the total section of each HP and its associated thermal insulation, n_{HP} is the total number of HPs and A_{sh} is the shielding section. Because the insulation surrounding each heat pipe has a very low thermal conductivity (Carbon Foam, $k_{ins} \approx 0.2 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ [6]) compared with that of the shielding material ($k_{sh} \approx 4.4 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$), the HP-insulation region is thus treated as void occupying a fraction p of the cross section. Each HP can transfer heat to the shielding by radial conduction through the thermal insulation annuli. The conductive heat from a heat pipe to the shielding at the radial position R_{HP} is:

$$Q_{HP} = \frac{2\pi L}{\ln(r_{IHP}/r_{HP})} k_{ins}(T_{HP} - T(R_{HP})) \quad (4)$$

Where T_{HP} is temperature of the heat pipe wall and $T(R_{HP})$ is the temperature at the shielding in the radial position R_{HP} .

The model includes an external thermal insulator mounted on the outer surface of the shield to reduce radiative heat losses, which are proportional to the fourth power of the external surface temperature.

$$Q_{loss} = \frac{2\pi k_{ins} L}{\ln\left(\frac{R_{insul}}{R_{sh}}\right)} [T(R_{insul}) - T(R_{sh})] = 2\pi R_{insul} L \varepsilon \sigma [T(R_{insul})^4 - T_{sink}^4] \quad (5)$$

Where R_{insul} is the external radius of the shielding surface thermal insulator.

By solving this set of equations setting the maximum shielding temperature and maximum radiative heat loss as constraints, the optimizer allows to determine the insulation thickness between the heat pipes and shielding, and the external thermal insulation required.

2.2. Optimization Methodology

The coupled reactor–shielding design is optimized using the metamodeling approach implemented in the PRESTO tool. The method combines database generation, interpolation, and constrained optimization. First, a database of possible reactor and shielding configurations with different geometrical dimensions is automatically generated. Data bases are generated out of SERPENT Monte Carlo simulations to obtain key reactor core and reactor shielding parameters (reaction rates, neutron and gamma fluxes and reactivity). Different thermal models are also used to estimate key thermal parameters (temperatures and heat fluxes) both in the reactor core and shielding. From these databases, interpolation functions are built to estimate for key parameters like reactivity, systems mass, neutron and gamma fluxes, among others.

In the optimization stage, these interpolation functions are used to minimize the total system mass for a given reactor power, under physical and geometric constraints. Reactor core design constraints include criticality and excess reactivity, temperature, and irradiation limits. Shielding design constraints include maximum neutron fluences, gamma doses, and material temperature. The coupling between both subsystems is restricted to geometric and thermal conditions, such as ensuring that the shielding fully covers the reactor shadow and accounting for the local reduction in density and heat transfer effects caused by the heat pipes crossing the LiH region as already discussed.

The thermal model of the shielding, described in Sec. 2.1, is used during the design process to estimate the required insulation thickness between the heat pipes and the LiH and the external insulation, when applicable, to satisfy the imposed temperature and the maximal heat-loss limits.

PRESTO solves the constrained optimization using a Lagrange multiplier–based algorithm to identify the configuration that minimizes total mass while fulfilling all the requirements and design and safety constraints.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Comparison between Coupled and Sequential Reactor-Shielding Design

Table 1 summarizes two optimization strategies: sequential and a coupled design optimization. In the sequential approach, the reactor design is first optimized independently using the reactor database under the imposed k_{eff} and power requirements. Once the optimal reactor is identified, the shielding is sized to ensure that neutron fluence and gamma dose limits are satisfied at the exit surface.

In contrast, in the coupled approach both reactor and shielding databases are used simultaneously to construct interpolation functions for the two subsystems and their mutual interactions. The optimization is then performed on the combined reactor–shielding system, allowing both reactor and shielding parameters to vary concurrently in order to minimize the total system mass while satisfying all neutronic, thermal and radiological constraints.

Both approaches impose $k_{eff}=1.03$, a thermal power of 50 kW, a maximum LiH temperature of 900 K (i.e. about 50 K below the melting point), and an arbitrary fixed maximum radiative loss of 15% through shielding surface. In all cases, the shielding must satisfy an averaged neutron-fluence limit of 1×10^{12} n/cm² and a gamma-dose limit of 1 Mrad at the exit surface.

As can be seen from Table I and also from Fig. 4 the coupled design optimization leads to a total mass (reactor core and shielding) about 180 kg lower than the sequential one for the core configuration with

height to diameter ratio (H/D) equal 1.1. Although the reactor core becomes slightly heavier in the coupled optimization, this increase is more than compensated by a larger reduction in shielding mass, especially in the gamma-shield section. In the sequential design, the reflector is thicker than the one obtained from the coupled optimization and the fuel region (defined by the apothem of the unit cell and the number of HPs) is smaller. A thicker light reflector decreases the neutron leaks and provide some moderation which allow saving heavy fuel. However, the overall core radius is larger resulting in a larger diameter shielding. Moreover, since the fuel volume is smaller, the power density is larger than in the fuel of the reactor core obtained from the coupled design (both designs have the same power output). Together, these effects raise the fission rate near the fuel boundary with the reflector, as can be seen from the fission rate profiles displayed in Figure 3 for the two designs, which increases the prompt-gamma leakage toward the shielding. Since the gamma-source current ($J_{\gamma, \text{leak}}$) is larger (in area and in magnitude), the optimizer must extend the gamma-shield length (L_{γ}) in order to satisfy the fluence and dose limits at the shield exit. Since the gamma-shielding has a greater density than the neutron-shielding (19.3 g/cm^3 and 0.8 g/cm^3) some centimeters increase adds significant mass. In addition, the sequential reactor has a slightly larger radius (R_{core}), which increases the shielding radius as well, adding mass on top of the longer gamma-shield section.

Table I. Summary of optimization results.

System	Parameter	Optimization type	
		Sequential	Coupled
Reactor	t_{refl} (cm)	13.2	8.8
	apot (cm)	2.7	3.2
	R_{core} (cm)	31.3	28.5
	$J_{n, \text{leak}}$ (n/s)	4.6×10^9	4.9×10^9
	$J_{\gamma, \text{leak}}$ (n/s)	3.5×10^9	2.4×10^9
	$\text{mass}_{\text{score}}$ (kg)	652	777
Shielding	R_{shield} (cm)	46.0	42.0
	$L_{\text{sh}, n}$ (cm)	69.3	77.5
	$L_{\text{sh}, \gamma}$ (cm)	7.0	5.8
	$\text{mass}_{\text{insul}}$ (kg)	16	18
	$\text{mass}_{\text{sh}, \gamma}$ (kg)	1005	717
	$\text{mass}_{\text{sh}, n}$ (kg)	495	505
Total	$\text{mass}_{\text{sh}, \text{tot}}$ (kg)	1515	1240
	$\text{mass}_{\text{system}}$ (kg)	2197	2017

Figure 3. Reactor axial fission density for the sequential (right) and coupled optimization (left).

Due to these reasons, the coupled optimization process reduces the reflector thickness and increases the fuel region. These actions reduce the gamma production in the bottom of the reactor reducing therefore the gamma current and lowering the gamma shielding length need. Even if the reactor mass increases slightly and the neutron current toward the shielding increases, the shielding becomes significantly lighter, resulting in the lower total mass obtained in the coupled design.

Both optimization processes, coupled and sequential, were carried out for different values of the height-to-diameter ratio (H/D) to investigate the effect of the reactor core shape on the optimization. The results are presented in Fig. 4. As can be seen, the coupled optimization process achieves the lowest total mass. The results also show an optimal H/D between 1.0 and 1.1. This optima value is mainly explained by the opposite effects of H/D on core neutron leakage and on the shielding cross-section.

Figure 4. System mass as function of reactor H/D ratio.

3.2. Parametric analysis of heat-loss constraint

Shielding neutron material LiH should remain under 965 K to avoid melting and therefore insulation between the 1000 K heat pipes and the shielding is needed. Moreover, the high operating temperature of the shielding can cause significant radiation heat losses into space, thus decreasing the heat transported by the heat pipes to the power conversion system. Therefore, an external insulation layer is required to decrease then the radiative heat loss. In this section we investigate the effect of these two thermal constraints in the optimization.

Figure 5. Total reactor core and shielding mass versus the heat loss through shielding expressed as fraction of the total reactor thermal power (50 kWth).

Figure 6. Temperatures in the shielding as function of the reactor heat-loss fraction. Thicknesses of both the heat-pipe thermal insulation ($t_{insul,HP}$) and the shielding thermal insulation ($t_{insul,sh}$) also shown.

Figure 5 shows the total mass of the reactor core and shielding subsystems as a function of the allowable radiative heat loss at the outer surface of the reactor shielding. For each point on the curves, the full system is optimized under the same constraints (50 kW thermal power, $T_{max} \leq 900$ K, $k_{eff} = 1.03$) while imposing different values for the maximum heat-loss fraction to space from the shielding. As can be seen from Fig. 5, as the allowed heat loss is reduced, the total system mass increases for all heat-pipe configurations (19, 37, and 61 HPs). This trend is mainly driven by the required insulation between the heat pipes and the shielding (LiH). When the heat loss is reduced, both thermal insulations must be

increased. In particular, the increase in thermal insulation between the heat pipes and the shielding significantly reduces the shielding's neutron attenuation, requiring an increase in its length, which leads to the rise in total mass observed in Fig. 5. Moreover, increasing the shielding length also increases the length of the heat pipes and adversely impacts heat transfer. This degradation prevents reducing the shielding radiation losses to space below a certain limit. As shown in Fig. 5, this limit increases with the number of heat pipes. Indeed, although heat-pipe radius decreases when more heat pipes are used for the same core thermal power (1.1 cm, 0.77cm and 0.6 cm for 19, 37 and 61 HPs respectively), the *total* heat-transfer area between the heat pipes and the shielding increases, and therefore more insulation is needed to limit the heat leaking into the LiH. Finally, to better understand the effect of the two thermal insulation, figure 6 illustrates, for 37-heat pipes reactors, the temperatures at the centre of the shielding $T_{max,shield}$, over its surface in contact with the external thermal insulation $T_{R,shield}$ and over the external insulation surface $T_{insul,ext}$. The insulation thickness between heat pipes and shielding and the external insulation thickness are also displayed versus the maximum allowed heat losses.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Using the multiphysics optimization tool PRESTO, we analyzed the coupled reactor-shielding system for 50-kWth Heat-Pipe Reactors (HPRs). Two optimization strategies were studied: sequential and a coupled design optimization. In the sequential design optimization, the reactor design is optimized first and the shielding is sized afterwards. In the coupled design, the reactor and shielding designs are optimized at the same time. The comparison between sequential and coupled optimization shows that optimizing both subsystems simultaneously lead to a reduction of about 10% in the total mass of the reactor core and shielding. Both optimization processes also showed that the optimal height-to-diameter ratio (H/D) for this specific reactor design lies between 1.0 and 1.1 when both reactor and shielding masses are minimized. This optima value is mainly explained by the opposite effects of H/D on core neutron leakage and on the shielding cross-section.

The studies further indicate that the shielding thermal constraints, namely the maximum allowable shield temperature and the maximum allowable heat loss to space, have a significant impact on HPR design. These two constraints require the use of thermal insulation around the heat pipes and on the outer surface of the shielding. However, the insulation around the heat pipes reduces shielding efficiency, leading to a substantial increase in shielding mass. The results suggest that, for a given core thermal power, the HPR configuration with the lowest number of heat pipes should be preferred.

The next step of this work will involve adding the power-conversion and radiator subsystems to enable a full NEP system design optimization.

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